

Moving Target Detection Via Digital Time Domain Correlation of Random Noise Radar Signals

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Abstract—Ultra-wideband random noise radar theoretically has a thumbtack ambiguity function, which cannot be realized due to hardware, processing, and environmental limitations. Velocity estimation using traditional Doppler processing is not practicable for ultra-wideband random noise radar because of the large fractional bandwidth. Through analysis, this paper explores moving target detection using digital correlation processing of random noise signals in the time domain with a single receive channel. Additionally, simulated and measured results are presented.

I. INTRODUCTION

Random noise radar (RNR) continuously transmits the bandlimited output of a thermal noise source. By design, the transmit signal typically has greater than 25% fractional bandwidth, and often between 50% and 100%, making it an ultra-wideband (UWB) signal. The wide fractional bandwidth and random nature of the signal results in traditional, spectral domain Doppler processing being impracticable. Alternatively, digital correlation processing in the time domain of dilated reference signals may be used to detect moving targets. Direct analog-to-digital conversion and digital signal processing techniques enable velocity detection in the time domain, though it requires significant computational resources that may prohibit real-time processing, using current hardware.

This paper explores two-dimensional cross-correlation using dilated and translated versions of a segment of the transmitted random noise waveform as the reference. Using wavelet terminology, translation is due to the time delay of the received signal due to target range, and dilation corresponds to compression and expansion of the waveform due to target's radial velocity. For narrowband signals, the time dilation results in a Doppler shift in the frequency domain.

This paper first presents an analytical model of AFIT's UWB RNR, which is based on Narayanan's design [1]. The digital correlation approach is then detailed with simulation and experimental results.

II. RADAR MODEL

Following Pace's notation [2, Sec 7.3] the bandlimited, random noise signal transmitted is modeled as

$$s(t) = X(t) \cos(2\pi f_c t) - Y(t) \sin(j2\pi f_c t), \quad (1)$$

where f_c is the center frequency of the waveform. $X(t)$ and $Y(t)$ are stationary, zero-mean Gaussian processes with

bandwidth B . In terms of complex signals $s(t) = \text{Real}[\psi(t)]$.

$$\psi(t) = u(t)e^{j2\pi f_c t}, \quad (2)$$

where $u(t) = X(t) + jY(t)$.

The received echo from a point target at a distance R with relative, radial velocity v with respect to the radar would be $\psi(\alpha t - t_d)$, where $t_d = 2R/(c - v) \approx 2R/c$ when $v \ll c$. The signal dilation due to the relative radial velocity is $\alpha = (c - v)/(c + v)$.

The cross-correlation of the received signal with a reference signal $\psi(\alpha_r t - t_r)$, which is translated (time delayed) by t_r and dilated (time compressed) by $\alpha_r = (c - v_r)/(c + v_r)$ is proportional to

$$C(t_d, \alpha; t_r, \alpha_r) = \int_t^{t+T} h(t-\zeta)\psi(\alpha\zeta - t_d)\psi^*(\alpha_r\zeta - t_r)d\zeta, \quad (3)$$

where T is the measurement time and $h(t)$ is a window function. Equation (3) represents the output of the matched filter and can be used to define the generalized ambiguity function. With the substitution of $\beta = \alpha/\alpha_r$ and $\Delta\tau = t_d - \beta t_r$, Axelsson defines the generalized ambiguity function of an UWB random waveform as [3]

$$|\chi(\beta, \Delta\tau)| = \left| \int_t \psi(\beta t - \Delta\tau)\psi^*(t)dt \right|. \quad (4)$$

Assuming $\psi(t)$ is ergodic, then Equation (4) becomes a time average over the measurement time T . So following Dawood's derivation [4] and making a single channel simplification gives the time average ambiguity function as

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle \chi(\beta, \Delta\tau, t) \rangle| &= \left| \text{Real} \left[\int_t^{t+T} E[\psi(\beta\zeta - \Delta\tau)\psi^*(\zeta)] \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \times h(t - \zeta)d\zeta \right] \right| \\ &= \left| \text{Real} \left[\int_t^{t+T} E[u(\beta\zeta - \Delta\tau)u^*(\zeta)] \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \times e^{j2\pi f_c(\beta-1)\zeta} h(t - \zeta)d\zeta \right] \right| \\ &= \left| \int_t^{t+T} R_u[(\beta-1)\zeta - \Delta\tau] \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times \cos(j2\pi f_c(\beta-1)\zeta)h(t - \zeta)d\zeta \right|, \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1. Block diagram of the AFIT random noise radar, which is based on Narayanan's design [1]. The primary difference is the AFIT UWB RNR uses a single receive channel.

Dawood and Narayanan give the analytical solution of autocorrelation function $R_u(\cdot)$ as [4]

$$R_u[(\beta - 1)\zeta - \Delta\tau] = \frac{\sin[\pi B((\beta - 1)\zeta - \Delta\tau)]}{\pi B((\beta - 1)\zeta - \Delta\tau)}. \quad (6)$$

Therefore, the ambiguity function for the AFIT noncoherent UWB RNR depicted in Figure 1 is

$$|\langle \chi(\beta, \Delta\tau, t) \rangle| = \left| \int_t^{t+T} \text{sinc}[\pi B((\beta - 1)\zeta - \Delta\tau)] \times \cos(j2\pi f_c(\beta - 1)\zeta)h(t - \zeta)d\zeta \right|, \quad (7)$$

where T is the measurement time, B is the signal bandwidth, f_c is the center frequency, and $h(t)$ is a window function. Figure 2 represents the ambiguity function over an array of reference velocities and ranges where a perfectly matched filter corresponds to $|\chi(0, 0, T)|$.

From the ambiguity function, the signal parameters that control velocity resolution were found to be the maximum frequency, f_H , in the bandwidth, B , and the measurement window, T . Figure 3 illustrates how velocity resolution depends on f_H and T equally. These parameters, in turn, control the number of samples, L , in the digital transmit and receive signals since $L = \lceil f_s \cdot T \rceil$ and $f_s \geq 2f_H$ in order to meet Nyquist. Therefore, accurate velocity detection requires many samples.

III. 2D DIGITAL CROSS CORRELATION AND RNR

Dawood and Narayanan [4] develop a generalized wideband ambiguity function for a coherent random noise radar. In the development of the ambiguity function, they note that the correlator must be matched to the range rate, as well as the delay of the target, due to the Doppler-spread parameter of UWB waveforms. Creating a correlation filter matched to the delay and range rate of the target has been discussed by Pace [2, Sec 7.3]; however, the authors are unaware of any attempts to implement this approach in the time domain

Figure 2. The ambiguity plot depicts the range and velocity resolutions for AFIT's random noise radar that operates with a bandwidth of $B = 400$ MHz, center frequency of $f_c = 550$ MHz, and a chosen measurement time of $T = 150$ ms.

utilizing a fully digital correlator. The likely reason for the reluctance to implement the two-dimensional filter is the computational requirements. The number of variables to be considered in the filter design and the range of those variables must be weighed carefully against the available computation resources, including time.

When implementing the digital correlator in the time domain, each discrete sample of the reference signal must be interpolated based on the time shift Δt that each sample experiences due to the time dilation of the returned signal corresponding to the reference velocity v_r . Recall $\alpha_r = (c - v_r)/(c + v_r)$. After every sample shifts in time, the reference signal's measurement time changes by $T_r = T/\alpha_r$. Therefore, the total time difference ΔT between the reference and transmitted signals is $\Delta T = T_r - T$. Assuming the target's radial velocity is constant over T , the relative time shift each sample experiences can be derived as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta t &= \frac{\Delta T}{f_s \cdot T} = \frac{T_r - T}{f_s \cdot T} = \frac{\frac{T}{\alpha} - T}{f_s \cdot T} \\ &= \frac{T \left(\frac{1}{\alpha} - 1 \right)}{f_s \cdot T} = \frac{\frac{c+v}{c-v} - 1}{f_s} = \frac{c+v - c+v}{(c-v) f_s} \\ &= \frac{2v}{(c-v) f_s} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where f_s represents the sampling frequency and a negative velocity corresponds to an ingressing target. Figure 4 illustrates how even though every sample experiences a relative time shift of Δt , the overall time shift that each sample gets interpolated by is

$$s_{ref}[k] = s[k - (k - 1)\Delta t] \quad (9)$$

(a) $f_H = 500$ MHz

(b) $T = 50$ ms

Figure 3. The ambiguity plot when perfectly matched in range, $\chi(\beta, 0, T)$. (a) The maximum frequency is fixed at 500 MHz while T is varied. (b) The measurement time is fixed at 50 ms while f_H is varied.

where $k \in 1 : L$ and L is the number of samples, $L = \lceil f_s \cdot T \rceil$ ($f_s \geq 2f_H$ to meet Nyquist).

After creating a reference signal that is matched to a particular reference velocity, range correlation can be quickly performed by

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathcal{F}^{-1} \{ \mathcal{F} \{ s_{ref} \}^* \cdot \mathcal{F} \{ s_r \} \}, \quad (10)$$

where \mathcal{F} represents the FFT, s_r is the received signal, and \mathbf{r} is a row vector that contains the matched filter responses for the reference time delays. The process can then be repeated to create a bank of match filter responses, \mathbf{C} .

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}_1 \\ \mathbf{r}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{r}_V \end{bmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

where V is the number of reference velocities used to create

Figure 4. In order to simulate reference signals, interpolation must be used so the sampling frequency f_s does not change. The top plot can be viewed as a transmit signal where the small dashed lines correspond to the sampled signal at a rate of f_s . The bottom plot would be a received/reference signal where the original samples, represented by large dashed lines, have shifted in time. In order to keep the same f_s as in the hardware, each sample is interpolated back to the original time locations represented again by the small dashed lines.

the bank of matched filters for the 2D digital correlation.

IV. RESULTS

MATLAB[®] was used to conduct the simulations following the steps below:

- 1) Create Gaussian distributed noise vector in double format of length $\lceil f_s \cdot T \rceil$.
- 2) Band-limit the noise vector.
- 3) Create received signal,
 - a) Using the simulated, band-limited, double formatted noise vector, interpolate the simulated received signal to the target's velocity v .
 - b) Translate the vector to accommodate for the target's time delay t_d .
 - c) Convert to 8-bit format.
- 4) Create reference signals,
 - a) Convert the simulated, band-limited, double formatted noise vector to 8-bit,
 - b) Interpolate one 8-bit noise vector for every reference velocity v_r ,
 - c) Translate each reference velocity noise vector for every reference time delay t_r .
- 5) Compute the inner product between the simulated received signal and bank of reference signals.
- 6) The largest inner product equates to the simultaneous range and velocity estimates for the target.

Results are shown in Figure 5 for a simulation for a 3 m/s matched filter, which was assumed to be perfectly matched in time delay. The simulation closely resembles the ambiguity function given in (7).

An experiment was then conducted that used a GPS enabled golf cart as the moving target. As the golf cart ingressed at a constant known velocity, the AFIT UWB RNR collected data once the target reached a known range of either five or ten meters. Then the digital signal processing (DSP) described in

Figure 5. The simulated matched filter response depicted here for a constant target radial velocity of 3 m/s over a measurement time T of 150 ms. The AFIT random noise radar parameters of $B = 400$ MHz and $f_c = 550$ MHz were used. This simulation assumed the matched filter was perfectly matched in time delay resulting in a very accurate velocity estimation.

Figure 7. Processed data where the target's velocity and range was -5 m/s and 5 m. The measurement time was 80 ms.

Figure 6. Processed data where the target's velocity and range was -3 m/s and 5 m. The measurement time was 160 ms.

Figure 8. Processed data where the target's velocity and range was -5 m/s and 10 m. The measurement time was 80 ms.

Section III produced the final output **C** shown in Figures 6-8. These figures illustrate the possible accuracy of simultaneous range and velocity estimation using digital correlation of UWB RNR in the time domain.

V. CONCLUSION

The results indicate digital correlation can effectively detect a moving target's range and velocity simultaneously. However, due to the number of samples needed, the processing and memory requirements are the major limiting factors prohibiting real-time operation. Research is on-going to optimize the digital correlation processing along with an investigation into using graphical processing units to increase processing throughput.

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